

THE PROBLEM OF EQUIVALENCE IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

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Abstract. Literary translation is a translation of a text done by translating each word separately without looking at how the words are used together in a phrase or sentence. This article describes about some problems of equivalence in literary translation.

Keywords: equivalence, types of translation, literary translation.

Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. The English language draws a terminological distinction between translating and interpreting; under this distinction, translation can begin only after the appearance. In formal language theory, equivalence of two grammars means they generate the same set of strings, i.e. that the formal language they generate is the same. The following three types of translation can be distinguished: equivalent translation, literal translation and free translation. Equivalent translation Equivalent translation has been considered in the preceding pages. Achieving equivalence is the goal aimed at in translation. Literal translation In spite of the fact that there are cases of semantic and structural coincidences they are rather an exception. A literal or word translation is obviously unacceptable because it results in a violation of form, or a distortion of sense, or both. In the event that we were to see up the word 'equivalence' within the word reference, we would likely discover this definition: "quality of that which is equivalent"; that's to say, when two realities or circumstances are compared, they are symmetrical to each other on the off chance that they show a relationship of coherent balance, in such a way that one of them is as it were genuine in case the other is as well. Be that as it may, in applying that etymological definition to the space of interpretation, we come over one of the most noteworthy regions of continuous discourse among pros in translation, and indeed phonetics in common. Usually since a few practical components are included within the endeavor at accomplishing solidarity, homogeneity, and comparability (in its strict meaning) between the interpreted content and the first.

Concurring to interpretation researcher Katharina Reiss, it is conceivable to approach the perfect of comparability in two ways: formal comparability and energetic proportionality. Formal proportionality grants the symmetrical transmission of a source content (or unique) into a deciphered content. Here,

the foremost vital model is the conservation of the canonical shape of the literary class and the strict interpretation of the words. On the other hand, energetic comparability is engrossed with holding not as it were the etymological proximity of the structure and of the words, but the feeling of the message as well; not wavering, for illustration, to adjust and adjust where essential. It may be said that the translator's part is in this way changed from one of guaranteeing literary proportionality and syntactic exactness into that of a co-author.

Taking these variables into consideration, it gets to be vital to dissect these two shapes of proportionality in interpretation. Firstly, one cannot deny that all interpretations performed by a competent interpreter stay reliable to the first content in a few way, whether by implies of formal or energetic proportionality. The quality of the interpretation will subsequently depend on what way of proportionality the interpreter chooses to take after within the execution of his work: either to substitute printed fabric in one dialect with denotatively comparable fabric within the other; or to form correspondence between the phonetic units, free of any thought of substance. In compiler theory the notion is distinguished from strong (or structural) equivalence, which additionally means that the two parse trees are reasonably similar in that the same semantic interpretation can be assigned to both. In semantics, the best-known types of semantic equivalence are dynamic equivalence and formal equivalence, which employ translation approaches that focus, respectively, on conveying the meaning of the source text; and that lend greater importance to preserving, in the translation, the literal structure of the source text. The "Formal-equivalence" approach emphasizes fidelity to the lexical details and grammatical structure of the source language, whereas "dynamic equivalence" tends to employ a rendering that is more natural to the target language. Because the functional equivalence approach eschews strict adherence to the grammatical structure of the original text in favor of a more natural rendering in the target language, it is sometimes used when the readability of the translation is more important than the preservation of the original grammatical structure.

Formal equivalence is often more goal than reality, if only because one language may contain a word for a concept which has no direct equivalent in another language. In such cases, a more dynamic translation may be used or a neologism may be created in the target language to represent the concept (sometimes by borrowing a word from the source language).

The more the source language differs from the target language, the more difficult it may be to understand a literal translation without modifying or rearranging the words in the target language. On the other hand, formal equivalence can allow readers familiar with the source language to analyze how meaning was expressed in the original text, preserving untranslated idioms, rhetorical devices and diction in order to preserve original information and highlight finer shades of meaning.

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